

Original article

Phenotypic detection of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and antimicrobial susceptibility patterns at University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Maiduguri

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Abstract

Background: *Staphylococcus aureus* is a major human pathogen responsible for a spectrum of infections ranging from superficial skin lesions to life-threatening conditions. Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) has emerged as a formidable nosocomial and community pathogen, as strains are resistant to all β -lactam antibiotics and frequently exhibit co-resistance to other drug classes, severely limiting therapeutic options. This study aimed to determine the prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) from clinical specimens at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital. **Materials and Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted between June and November 2024. Two hundred and twenty (220) *Staphylococcus aureus* clinical isolates were confirmed, and susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method. MRSA was identified by resistance to a 30 μ g cefoxitin disk. The antibiotic panel included ampicillin, gentamicin, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, chloramphenicol, tetracycline, clindamycin, mupirocin, fusidic acid, linezolid, amikacin, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and cefuroxime. **Results:** Of the 220 *S. aureus* isolates, 15.0% (n=33) were MRSA. Wound swabs constituted the largest specimen group (42.3%) and yielded the highest proportion of MRSA among wound samples (23.7%). All MRSA (100%) were resistant to ampicillin, 81.8% to cefuroxime, 75.8% to erythromycin, 78.8% to trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and 63.6% to ciprofloxacin. Linezolid retained the highest activity (90.9% susceptible), followed by fusidic acid and amikacin (87.9% each). **Conclusion:** The study confirms a substantial MRSA burden, with high resistance to commonly used antibiotics. These findings underscore the need for intensified infection control and antimicrobial stewardship in this setting.

Keywords: MRSA, MDR, Phenotypic characterization, UMTH

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Introduction

Staphylococcus aureus is an important pathogen in human infections as it is implicated in a wide range of infections, from mild skin infections to more serious and invasive infections, including sepsis, pneumonia, endocarditis, deep-seated abscesses, suppuration, and also pyogenic infections and toxinoses such as food poisoning and toxic shock syndrome.¹ Over the decades, some strains of *Staphylococci*, such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), have developed resistance to antibiotics that were previously used against them. MRSA strains, though first reported in 1961, did not become a major problem until the late 1970s and early 1980s, when outbreaks were reported from many parts of the world.²

Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is resistant to methicillin, amoxicillin, penicillin, oxacillin, and many other antibiotics. They are also resistant clinically to all beta-lactam antibiotics, despite apparent in vitro efficacy.ⁱⁱⁱ It is also important to note that MRSA is often multidrug-resistant and is resistant to antibiotics such as the macrolides and aminoglycosides.¹ Numerous studies have indicated that *Staphylococcus aureus* is among the most frequently encountered microorganisms in medical microbiology laboratories from clinical samples in Nigeria.^{iv,v,vi,vii} The scientific advances regarding the genetic origin of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* have led to a greater understanding of MRSA epidemiology in Nigeria. Not until recently has MRSA been predominantly a nosocomial pathogen that causes hospital-acquired infections; however, MRSA strains are now increasingly isolated from community-acquired infections as well.^{viii} Vancomycin has been the antibiotic of choice for MRSA infections, and the emergence of vancomycin-nonsusceptible *Staphylococcus aureus* reported in recent years is a cause of great public health concern, making therapy of MRSA infections even more challenging for clinicians.^{9,10} Vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (VISA) has now been reported from patients worldwide.¹¹ Resistance in Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is mediated by the presence of penicillin-binding protein (PBP)-2a, encoded by the chromosomal *mecA* gene.¹² Penicillin-binding protein PBP-2a is a cell wall enzyme with low affinity for β -lactam antibiotics; independent of β -lactamase production, it allows cell wall formation at drug concentrations that render the other PBPs inactive.¹³ The number of hospitals affected by MRSA has increased significantly in the past five years, with the prevalence of MRSA increasing over the years.^{14,15,16}

There are increasing reports of MRSA strains involved in clinical infections in Nigeria.^{8,9} *Staphylococcus aureus* is responsible for more than one-third of surgical wound infections and MRSA was found to be up to 30% in most cases.^{16,17,27} Most of these strains are detected by phenotypic testing with oxacillin and methicillin disks. A ceftioxin disk was introduced a few years ago to test *Staphylococcus aureus* for expression of methicillin resistance, and it was found to be reliable.^{25,27} Although detection of the *mecA* gene by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) is the gold standard for MRSA confirmation, only a few studies in Nigeria have used this method.^{xvi} This test is also not available for use in most routine diagnostic laboratories. The objectives of this study are to determine the prevalence rate of methicillin resistance and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of *S. aureus* clinical isolates at UMTH Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

Materials and methods

This is a prospective study and the clinical isolates of *S. aureus* from different specimens including wound swab, blood, urine, pus, sputum and other specimens between June to November 2024 at the Medical Microbiology Laboratory of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital. Two hundred and twenty (220) strains of *S. aureus* isolated from patients admitted or are attending our OPD were included. The specimens were processed according to recommended guidelines by first culturing on Mannitol salt agar (Oxoid Ltd, Cambridge, UK) and incubating at 37°C for 24 hours.²⁸ *S. aureus* isolates were identified by colonial morphology and fermentation reactions on Mannitol salt agar, Gram stain, catalase, tube coagulase, and deoxyribonuclease (DNAase) tests.¹⁷

Phenotypic detection of MRSA

This was carried out in accordance with the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute guidelines. Pure cultures of each *S. aureus* isolate and the control strain were utilised. For each isolate and control strain, five colonies were transferred to 5 mL of nutrient broth and incubated overnight at 35°C. The resulting overnight cultures were then diluted with sterile saline (0.85% NaCl) in Bijou bottles, and their turbidity was compared to 0.5

McFarland standards. The inocula were spread on Mueller–Hinton agar supplemented with 2% NaCl (Oxoid Ltd) using a sterile cotton wool swab. Cefoxitin (30 µg) disks (Oxoid Ltd) were applied with sterile forceps, and the agar plates were aerobically incubated for 16-18 hours at 35°C.

The diameter of the inhibition zone (ZD) for each isolate was measured and then compared to the interpretative standard for ZD. As control strains, MRSA American-type cultures from the ATCC 25923 and ATCC 700699 collections (Bio-Mérieux France) were used as negative and positive controls, respectively.

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing

The Kirby–Bauer disk diffusion method was used to assess susceptibility to 12 antibiotics (e.g., ampicillin, gentamicin, ciprofloxacin). Results were interpreted using CLSI criteria (2023), categorising isolates as sensitive, intermediate, or resistant. The susceptibility of *S. aureus* isolates to various antibiotics ampicillin (10 µg), gentamicin (10 µg), erythromycin (15 µg), ciprofloxacin (5 µg), chloramphenicol (30 µg) tetracycline (30 µg), clindamycin (2 µg), mupirocin (20µg), fusidic acid (10µg), linezolid (30µg), amikacin(30µg) trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole(1.25µg/23.75µg), using the modified Kirby–Bauer disk diffusion method. The interpretation of results is based on established guidelines, and the isolates are categorised as sensitive, intermediately resistant, or resistant to each antibiotic.²⁹

Study Design

A cross-sectional laboratory-based study was conducted at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH).

Study Population

Clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* were obtained from patients presenting with suspected bacterial infections or admitted to UMTH, regardless of age or gender.

Study duration.: This study was conducted between June to November 2024

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion: Confirmed *S. aureus* isolates from wound swabs, blood, sputum, urine, pus, CSF and aspirates at the time of the study.

Exclusion: Mixed bacterial cultures, non-*S. aureus* isolates, or samples with incomplete demographic data.

Sampling Method

Consecutive sampling of 220 confirmed *S. aureus* isolates meeting the inclusion criteria over a 6-month study period was employed.

Ethical consideration: Approval for this study was obtained from the Ethics committee of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital Ref No (ADM/TH/497/VOL 1). All patients' information was kept confidential.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS v26 software package (SPSS; IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY, USA). Frequency tables were generated, and analyses were performed using appropriate statistical tools, with resistance patterns expressed as percentages.

Results

A total of 220 non-duplicate specimens yielding *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates were included in the study. Of the clinical isolates acquired, 149 (67.7%) were from inpatients and 71 (32.3%) were from outpatients. Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) was isolated from 33 specimens, comprising 15.0% of all *S. aureus* isolates; specifically, 18 (12.1%) of the inpatient isolates and 15 (21.1%) of the outpatient isolates were identified as MRSA. The study population spans ages from 0 to greater than 60 years, as shown in Table 1. The age group 20-29 years had the highest MRSA prevalence rate, 13 (39.4%). Males constituted the majority of the study population, 120(54.5%). MSSA were the most prevalent strain of *S. aureus* cultured during the study period, 187 (85%), while MRSA were the least prevalent, 33 (15%).

S. aureus was largely isolated from wound swab 93(42.3%), with a prevalence of 23% MRSA; the least prevalence of MRSA was recorded in the blood sample, 6.9%. It is interesting to note that no MRSA was cultured from CSF, Aspirates, and sputum. Table 2

Table: 1 Sociodemographic distribution of staphylococcus strains

Variable	Number Staph. Aureus (220) n (%)	MSSA (187) n (%)	MRSA (33) n (%)	X ²	P value
Age (years)				12.93	0.0240
0-9	10 (4.5)	3(3.7)	3(9.1)		
10-19	32 (14.5)	27(14.4)	5(15.2)		
20-29	48 (21.8)	35(18.7)	13(39.4)		
30-39	55 (25.0)	47(25.1)	8(24.2)		
40-59	45 (20.5)	42(22.5)	3(9.1)		
≥ 60	30 (13.7)	29(15.5)	1(3.0)		
Gender				0.84	0.3579
Male	120 (54.5)	99(52.9)	21(63.6)		
Female	100 (45.5)	88(47.1)	12(36.4)		
Residence				7.90	0.0049*
Urban	135 (61.4)	122(65.2)	13(39.4)		
Rural	85 (38.6)	65(34.8)	20(60.6)		
Admission				3.08	0.0789
Yes	149 (67.7)	131(70.1)	18(54.5)		
No	71 (32.3)	56	15(45.5)		

Antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of MRSA

Out of the 33 MRSA detected, 30(90%) were susceptible to linezolid, 29 (87.9%) to fusidic acid and Amikacin respectively, only about 27 (81.8%) were susceptible to mupirocin and chloramphenicol respectively. All the 33(100%) MRSA were resistant to Ampicillin, and the second highest resistance was recorded for cefuroxime 27(81.8%), followed by erythromycin 25(75.8%) and then ciprofloxacin (61.6%). (Fig 1)

Discussion

This study focused on the occurrence of MRSA among patients attending the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital. In our study 15.0% of the isolates were found to be MRSA by cefoxitin disc diffusion method, which was comparable with the range reported in a systemic review by Abubakar et.al.³⁰

Table 2: Distribution of S. aureus isolates by clinical specimen

Organism	Wound Swabs n (%)	Urine n (%)	Blood n (%)	CSF n (%)	Sputum n (%)	Pus n (%)	Aspirates n (%)	Total
<i>S. aureus</i>	93(42.3)	11(5.0)	58(26.4)	6(2.7)	10(4.5)	38(17.2)	4(1.8)	220 (100)
MSSA	71(76.3)	10(90)	54(93.1)	6(100)	10(100)	32(84.2)	4(100)	187(85%)
MRSA	22(23.7)	1(10)	4(6.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	6(15.8)	0(0.0)	33(15%)

Figure 1. Susceptibility patterns of MRSA to different antibiotics

This alignment suggests a shared epidemiological profile in certain clinical settings. In contrast, our study found a lower prevalence than that reported in a multinational study by Kesah et al., which reported 28.2%.¹⁷ This may be due to the study's large sample size. A lower prevalence rate of 12.5% was reported by Okon et al. in a similar tertiary care setting in northeastern Nigeria.⁸ This disparity may be attributed to a combination of methodological and contextual factors. One plausible explanation is our study's design, which prioritised samples from both outpatients and inpatients with the highest susceptibility to nosocomial infections; this sampling focus may inherently yield a higher estimate of resistant pathogens. Furthermore, the specific protocols for specimen selection could have influenced the outcomes. Alternatively, the difference may signal a genuine temporal increase in MRSA burden, potentially fueled by the widespread and often prolonged use of antibiotics alongside suboptimal implementation of infection control measures.^{8, 9} Additionally, our findings contrast with those reported by Nwankwo et al., who documented a modestly higher MRSA prevalence of 28.6%, this may be attributable to differences in study design or the specific patient populations sampled.²¹ Our results also fall within the lower range of a wider spectrum of national data, exemplified by the considerably higher prevalence (31%) reported by Fayomi et al. in a different regional context.³¹

MRSA was predominantly cultured from male patients, whereas MSSA was more commonly cultured from female patients. Even though this study was not designed to identify risk factors for MRSA. This difference could have arisen from the fact that male patients constituted the majority of the study population and from differences in health-seeking behaviour for surgical illness between the two genders. The present investigation depicted that the prevalence of MRSA and MSSA isolated from wound swabs was the highest in comparison to other clinical samples. This result is consistent with the findings reported by Adhikari et al. in Nepal.³²

The highest isolation rate of *S. aureus* and MRSA in wound swab in our study could partly be due to the fact that wound samples came from the surgical wards of the hospital.

MRSA is increasingly prevalent in surgical wards, particularly in patients who have stayed long in the hospital.

Interestingly, the majority of *S. aureus* isolates were from specimens cultured from patients between the ages 20-29 years, this is in keeping with what was found in a study carried out Sokoto Nigeria by Adeiza et al.³³ This can be attributed to the fact the younger people may have close skin to skin contact more often during sports or when working.

The resistance profile observed severely limits therapeutic options, with high rates of resistance to ciprofloxacin (63.6%), erythromycin (75.8%), gentamicin (69.7%), and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (78.8%), and complete resistance to ampicillin. This trend of extensive non- β -lactam resistance among MRSA isolates, which corroborates the findings of Shittu et al. (%) in southwestern Nigeria, highlights a significant regional challenge for infection management.¹⁷ The higher rate of resistance observed in penicillin (100%) is in line with the results in the studies by Shrestha et al (91.94%),³⁵ and Ansari et al (94.7%).³⁶ This is probably due to the indiscriminate and empirical use of these drugs. Further, quinolones are relatively cheaper and easily available as over-the-counter drugs in Maiduguri. Moreover, Maiduguri is among the northeastern states that are battling with insurgency, and the majority of its indigenes are living below the poverty line, owing to economic constraints, lack of health facilities and lack of awareness towards drug resistance.

This study reveals a distinct pattern of antibiotic resistance, characterised by markedly higher rates of resistance to commonly used agents compared to less frequently prescribed alternatives. This trend aligns with the broader understanding that MRSA frequently exhibits multi-drug resistance; this finding is in keeping with what was found in a study by Kandle et al. in Maharashtra.³⁷ Isolates exhibited significant resistance to erythromycin (75.8%) and is consistent with the 75% resistance found by Ajantha et al.³⁸

Conclusion:

The findings of this study underscore the importance of regular laboratory surveillance for HAIs and strict adherence to antimicrobial stewardship within and outside the hospital. Health education and IPC policies may help reduce this menace.

References

1. Brooks G, Butel J, Morse S, Mietzner T, Adelberg E. The Staphylococci. In: Medical Microbiology. 23rd ed. New York: McGraw Hill; 2004.
2. Chambers HF. The changing epidemiology of *Staphylococcus aureus*? Emerg Infect Dis. 2001;7(2):178-82.
3. Bush K, Bradford PA. β -Lactams and β -lactamase inhibitors: an overview. Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med. 2016;6(8):a025247.
4. Legbo JN, Legbo JF. Bacterial isolates from necrotizing fasciitis: a clinico-pathological perspective. Niger J Med. 2007; 16:143-7.
5. Anah MU, Udo JJ, Ochigbo SO, Abia-Bassey LN. Neonatal septicaemia in Calabar, Nigeria. Trop Doct. 2008; 38:126-8.
6. Odetoyin WB, Aboderin AO, Ikem RT, Kolawole BA, Oyelese AO. Asymptomatic bacteriuria in patients with diabetes mellitus in Ile-Ife, South-West, Nigeria. East Afr Med J. 2008; 85:18-23.
7. Obidike EO, Anigbo G, Igbodo C. Sensitivity pattern of bacterial isolates in childhood sepsis in clinical practice at Onitsha. Niger J Clin Pract. 2009; 12:302-5.
8. Okon KO, Basset P, Uba A, Lin J, Oyawoye B, Shittu AO, et al. Co-occurrence of predominant Panton-Valentine leukocidin-positive sequence type (ST) 152 and multidrug-resistant ST 241 *Staphylococcus aureus* clones in Nigerian hospitals. J Clin Microbiol. 2009; 47:3000-3.
9. Ako-Nai AK, Lamikanra AB, Onipede AO. Incidence of pathogenic microorganisms in clinical specimens from hospitals in southwestern Nigeria. East Afr Med J. 1995; 72(7):436-41.
10. Oliveira DC, Tomasz A, de Lencastre H. The evolution of pandemic clones of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*: identification of two ancestral genetic backgrounds and the associated *mec* elements. Microb Drug Resist. 2001;7(4):349-61.
11. Adebayo S, Johnson L, Debaye K. Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of *S. aureus* and characterization of MRSA in southern Nigeria. Wounds. 2006; 18(4):77-84.
12. Ghamba PE, Mangoro ZM, Waza DE. Reoccurrence and distribution of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* MRSA in clinical specimens in Bauchi, North eastern Nigeria. J Med Med Sci. 2012; 3(8):506-11.
13. Siddiqui AH, Koirala J. Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. [Updated 2023 Apr 2]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK482221/>
14. Titanium antibacterial spinal systems. *Staphylococci. methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus* [Internet]. 1998 [updated 2009; cited 2012 Jun 17]. Available from: <http://www.silverspine.org/mrsa.html>
15. Appelbaum PC. Microbiology of antibiotic resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus*. Clin Infect Dis. 2007;45 Suppl 3: S165-70.
16. Shariati A, Dadashi M, Moghadam MT, van Belkum A, Yaslianifard S, Darban-Sarokhalil D. Global prevalence and distribution of vancomycin resistant, vancomycin intermediate and heterogeneously vancomycin intermediate *Staphylococcus aureus* clinical isolates: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Sci Rep. 2020;10(1):12689.
17. Peacock SJ, Paterson GK. Mechanisms of methicillin resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus*. Annu Rev Biochem. 2015; 84:577-601.
18. Fishovitz J, Hermoso JA, Chang M, Mobashery S. Penicillin-binding protein 2a of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. IUBMB Life. 2014;66(8):572-7.
19. Shittu AO, Okon K, Adesida S, Oyedara O, Witte W, Strommenger B, et al. Antibiotic resistance and molecular epidemiology of *Staphylococcus aureus* in Nigeria. BMC Microbiol. 2011; 11:92.
20. Okesola AO, Oni AA, Bakare RA. Prevalence and antibiotic sensitivity pattern of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in Ibadan, Nigeria. J Hosp Infect. 1999; 41(1):74-5.
21. Nwankwo BOK, Abdulhadi S, Magagi A, Ihesiulor G. Methicillin resistant *S.*

- aureus* (MRSA) and their antibiotic sensitivity pattern in Kano, Nigeria. *Afr J Clin Exper Microbiol.* 2010; 11(1):129-36.
22. Samuel SO, Kayode OO, Musa OI, Nwigwe GC, Aboderin AO, Salami TAT, et al. Nosocomial infection and the challenges of control in developing countries. *Afr J Clin Exper Microbiol.* 2010; 11(2):102-10.
 23. Oni AA, Bakare RA, Okesola AO, Ogunlowo HA, Ewete AF. Pattern of bacterial pathogens in surgical wound infections. *Afr J Med Med Sci.* 1997;26(3-4):139-40.
 24. Egbe CE, Omoregie R, Igarumah IO, Onemu S. Microbiology of wound infections and its associated risk factors among patients of a tertiary hospital in Benin City, Nigeria. *J Res Health Sci.* 2011;11(2):109-13.
 25. Odonkor ST, Addo KK. Evaluation of three methods for detection of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). *Int J Biol Med Res.* 2011;2(4):1031-4.
 26. Cauwelier B, Gordts B, Descheemaeker P, Van Landuyt HW. Evaluation of a disk diffusion method with cefoxitin (30 µg) for detection of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis.* 2004; 23:389-92.
 27. Olowe OA, Kukoyi OO, Taiwo SS, Ojurongbe O, Opaleye OO, Bolaji OS, et al. Phenotypic and molecular characteristics of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Infect Drug Resist.* 2013; 6:87-92.
 28. Cheesbrough M. *District Laboratory Practice in Tropical Countries.* 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2000. p. 64-7.
 29. Kesah C, Ben Redjeb S, Odugbemi TO, Boye CS, Dosso M, Ndinya Achola JO, et al. Prevalence of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in eight African hospitals and Malta. *Clin Microbiol Infect.* 2003;9(2):7-10.
 30. Abubakar U, Sulaiman SAS. Prevalence, trend and antimicrobial susceptibility of Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in Nigeria: a systematic review. *J Infect Public Health* (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2018.05.013>
 31. Fayomi OD, Ojo OE, Oyediran IA, Adeyemo AT. Methicillin-Resistance *Staphylococcus aureus* Among In-Patients at A Tertiary Health Facility in Ido-Ekiti, Nigeria. *Internet J Lab Med.* 2009;4(1):1-5.
 32. Adhikari P, Basyal D, Rai JR, et al. Prevalence, antimicrobial susceptibility pattern and multidrug resistance of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from clinical samples at a tertiary care teaching hospital: an observational, cross-sectional study from the Himalayan country, Nepal. *BMJ Open* 2023; 13:e067384. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2022-067384
 33. Adeiza SS, Onaolapo JA, Olayinka BO. Prevalence, risk-factors, and antimicrobial susceptibility profile of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) obtained from nares of patients and staff of Sokoto state-owned hospitals in Nigeria. *GMS Hyg Infect Control.* 2020;15:Doc25.DOI: 10.3205/dgkh000360, URN: urn:nbn:de:0183-dgkh000360
 34. Kolawole DO, Shittu AO. Epidemiological Analysis of Clinical Isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* in Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *Pak J Biol Sci.* 2005;7(6):1016-20.
 35. Bidya Shrestha, Bharat M Pokrel, Tribhuban M Mohapatra Phenotypic characterization of nosocomial isolates of staphylococcus aureus with reference to MRSA *J infect. Dev. countries* 2009;3(7);554-560
 36. Shamshul Ansari, Rajesh Kumar Jha, Shyam Kumar Mishara, Birenda Raj Tiwari, Ahmed Morad Asaad Recent Advances in *Staphylococcus aureus* infection; Focus on vaccine development. *Infection and drug resistance* 2019;12 1243-1255
 37. Kandle SK, Ghatole MP, Takpere AY, Hattiholi VV, Yemul VL. Bacteriophage typing and antibiotic sensitivity pattern of *Staphylococcus aureus* from clinical specimen in and around Solapur (South Maharashtra). *J Commun Dis.* 2003;35(1):17-23.
 38. Ajantha GS, Kulkarni RD, Shetty J, Shubhada C, Jain P. Phenotypic detection of inducible clindamycin resistance among *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates by using the lower limit of recommended inter-disk distance. *Indian J Pathol Microbiol.* 2008;51(3):376-8